

DETERMINANTS OF THE MANIFESTATION OF TOLERANCE IN TEACHERS

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Annotation. *This article describes the manifestation of types of tolerance in teachers and the functions of tolerance, ethnic tolerance, social tolerance and tolerance as a personal trait. In addition, the results of research conducted by the author on the manifestation of tolerance traits in teachers are highlighted. It is recognized that the factors determining the manifestation of social tolerance in teachers can be divided into several groups, such as personal characteristics, socio-psychological factors, professional experience and socio-cultural environment. Based on the study of studies devoted to the content, essence, appearance, types of tolerance traits, the author's definition of the concept of tolerance in a teacher is presented.*

Key words: *tolerance, social, emotional, physical, and social interaction, relationships, personal, psychology*

Аннотация. *В данной статье описываются проявления видов толерантности у педагогов, функции толерантности, этнической толерантности, социальной толерантности и толерантности как личностной черты. Кроме того, освещаются результаты исследования, проведенного автором по изучению проявления черт толерантности у педагогов. Отмечено, что факторы, определяющие проявление социальной толерантности у педагогов, можно разделить на несколько групп: личностные характеристики, социально-психологические факторы, профессиональный опыт и социокультурная среда. На основе изучения исследований, посвященных содержанию, сущности, проявлениям, видам черт толерантности, представлено авторское определение понятия толерантности педагога.*

Ключевое слово: *толерантность, социальное, эмоциональное, физическое и социальное взаимодействие, отношения, личностный аспект, психология.*

It is a psychological characteristic expressed in the ability to maintain a spirit of tolerance, forgiveness, equality, respect for the dignity of a student or group of students and the pedagogical team, and readiness to correctly accept various situations and circumstances in educational institutions.[5]

In psychology, self-control, endurance, patience, determination, courage, discipline, perseverance, independence, and courage are included in the qualities of will. Goal-orientedness is the ability of a person to focus all his strength on a goal he has set, to subordinate his actions to the task of achieving the intended goal, and to strive to achieve the goal despite any difficulties and obstacles. Self-control is a quality of will that is reflected in the ability to control a person's actions, emotions, and behavior. Endurance is a positive quality that reflects a person's desire to achieve his goal, often despite cold and heat, hunger and thirst, illness and other similar difficulties, overcoming all obstacles and achieving his goal.

Determination is a virtue that consists in a person's ability to quickly assess the situation, make a well-founded, thoughtful and firm decision in a timely manner, and proceed to implement it without hesitation. Discipline is a human quality expressed in voluntary and conscious obedience to the laws of society, moral norms and rules, national (universal) customs.[6]

According to Uzbek psychologists E.Goziev and R.Toshimov, tolerance is considered as a national psychological characteristic of a higher school teacher, explaining it as follows: “A person’s tolerance is expressed in his attitude towards relative, private, secondary, ordinary events, in reflecting the fact that they are a situation, a state related to gender and age. It is also directly manifested in the removal of etiquette, unpleasant experiences, and the consequences of conflicting situations from his mental world, in not holding grudges, not seeing them, not noticing them: - in the process of communication, in the relative assessment of realities outside the classroom; - in the removal of the consequences of experiences, situations from his mental world; in completely forgetting unpleasant relationships between team members, parents, in recognizing the universal, social value of confession, recognition, and apology. in understanding, in understanding that a flawless, perfect, perfect human being is a miracle of nature and society, etc.

Conclusion. Scientists of each theory have distinguished the following areas of tolerance: age tolerance - the correct acceptance of a person's age-related peculiarities (the inability of adults to understand young people, the lack of necessary knowledge and experience, etc.); tolerance related to the level of education - being patient with the thoughts and actions of people with a relatively low level of education; interethnic tolerance - treating representatives of different nationalities with respect, not considering the shortcomings and negative actions of a representative of one nationality to be also present in other people of the same nationality; racial tolerance - not looking down on representatives of other races; religious tolerance - treating different religions, confessions, and confessional groups with social tolerance; cultural tolerance - the ability to recognize other cultures and accept them correctly, contrary to cultural curiosity.

Cultural tolerance requires the exclusion of cultural influence and cultural expansion; interpersonal tolerance is the ability to understand and accept the complex nature of people, the differences between them, and the ability of a person to see others as a higher embodiment of his own existence and development in the process of communication.[5] Therefore, it is necessary to conduct extensive research to identify the types of tolerance in educators.

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